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LANGUAGE AND SPEECH RELATIONS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION
(Linguodidactic Analysis)

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ABSTRACT

Let's consider one possible way to introduce prefixes, suffixes, and endings. The methodological approach is determined, on the one hand, by the interaction of all morphemes in a word, and on the other, by the similarity of the word-formation functions of prefixes and suffixes and the unique grammatical function of endings. Taking this into account, the most appropriate approach is to use a word-formation task, during which students are presented with a group of cognate words formed using specific morphemes and visually understand their role.

Keywords: Language and speech relations, linguodidactic analysis, learning, education, pedagogy, psychology, native language.

Human speech is more than just a way to communicate and exchange information. Above all, it is a psychophysical portrait of the individual. The way people express themselves immediately reveals their level of education, worldview, passions, and interests. The primary period of development of correct speech in typically developing children occurs during preschool age—this is the most sensitive period. Subsequently, according to the renowned psychologist L.S. Vygotsky's classification of speech development periods during ontogenesis, a renewed surge in linguistic abilities, associated with the development of imagination and cultural perception, occurs between the ages of 8 and 9. Language is the primary means of human communication;

through language, people express their feelings, thoughts, and needs. Speech can be oral or written. Therefore, it is crucial to develop a person's speaking, reading, and writing skills[18].

Language is a complex system that includes specific rules of pronunciation, spelling, and construction of words and sentences. The chaotic use of words and the ability to speak and write without rules leads to misunderstandings, as happened with the builders of the Tower of Babel in the Old Testament story when they began speaking different languages.

By studying the origins of Russian words, students significantly broaden their horizons and gain knowledge about the history of our homeland, as well as the countries from which Russian words are borrowed[3].

By mastering the language, children learn thousands of new concepts from social relations, science, and culture. Language connects generations; it preserves and transmits folk wisdom.

A teacher's primary task is to instill in students a love for their native language and to teach them to understand its role and importance. Only truly exemplary speech should be heard in Russian language lessons; sloppy speech or haphazardly concocted examples should not be tolerated. Promoting speech culture is also a means of education.

Creative speech exercises (stories and essays) offer enormous educational potential. Essays foster self-esteem and self-confidence, develop interest in academic work, and promote understanding of all language work, particularly spelling and grammar. They foster activity and engagement, requiring reflection on what has been experienced, seen, and learned. Essays are one of the few academic activities in school that give students the opportunity to express themselves and their individuality.

By teaching students to craft their own stories, teachers give them the opportunity to learn how to structure their speech correctly and add stylistic nuance to their texts. This work can be compared to the work of an artist. While listening to a story, images emerge in a person's imagination that correspond to the purpose of the utterance: kind,

bright, beautiful, or perhaps sad, funny, or even scary. Everything depends on the words and the order in which they are constructed that the author uses in the story. Understanding these consequences, students develop a different approach to the choice and use of words in their speech. [11].

Thus, the need for language education goes far beyond the ability to write, read, and speak correctly. Language is used in all areas of human activity. A teacher, by utilizing all the aforementioned human capacities for using language in life, helps students understand the value of language education.

The content and types of native language classes in elementary grades consist of:

- developing students' oral and written speech—through reading, writing, grammar, observation, and social activities;
- teaching literacy to children entering first grade, i.e., basic reading and writing, and further refining these skills, turning them into habits;
- studying literary norms—correct spelling and punctuation, correct orthoepic pronunciation, and mastering expressiveness and stylistic elements;
- studying theoretical material on grammar, phonetics, and vocabulary, and developing systems of scientific concepts related to language;
- introducing students to examples of fiction, popular science, and other literature through reading and grammar lessons, and helping them master the ability to perceive literary works[9].

The teacher allocates the teaching hours allocated for the full course of study in the relevant subject by developing a curriculum in accordance with the national curriculum, which is a set of requirements mandatory for the implementation of basic educational programs, including primary education.

The curriculum is typically designed for an academic year or grade level. When developing the curriculum, the following factors are taken into account:

- the educational institution's goals and values;
- the students' health;
- their ability level;

- the nature of their academic motivation;
- the quality of academic achievement;
- educational needs;
- the teacher's capabilities;
- the state of the educational institution's educational, methodological, and logistical support.

Developing a curriculum, which is a fairly complex educational and regulatory document, requires a high level of qualification from its author/compiler.

Based on the objectives of teaching schoolchildren their native language, the goals of education and development, and relying on methodological foundations—the theory of knowledge and related sciences—methodology advances its own principles of teaching native languages, principles that define the main areas of a teacher's educational work[11]. These principles are as follows:

The principle of attention to the substance of language, the development of speech organs, and the proper development of speech skills. Any disregard for the patterns of speech and language negatively impacts the acquisition of practical speech activity. Thus, it has been established that underestimating pronunciation and phonetic skills leads to deficiencies in spelling literacy. This teaching principle requires the provision of auditory and visual aids in language lessons and the training of speech organs (pronunciation, expressive reading, internal pronunciation, etc.).

The principle of understanding linguistic meanings, both lexical and grammatical, morphemic, and syntactic. To understand a word, morpheme, phrase, or sentence means to relate them to specific phenomena of reality. Words and other units of language can also be learned in isolation from their meanings, but such assimilation, firstly, does not meet the goals of comprehensive personal development, and secondly, hinders the assimilation of language as a sign system. The condition for observing the principle of understanding linguistic meanings is the interconnected study of all aspects of language, all linguistic disciplines: grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, spelling, stylistics—their mutual penetration. Thus, morphology cannot be studied, understood,

or learned without relying on syntax, and syntax cannot be understood without relying on morphology; spelling is based on phonetics, grammar, word formation, etc. Morphemic analysis of a word helps to understand its meaning; On the other hand, analyzing the meaning of a word, as understood from context, will help with its morphemic analysis. Everything in language is interconnected, and this interconnectedness cannot be ignored in teaching[15].

The principle of developing a sense of language. Language is an extremely complex phenomenon; it is impossible to remember it without grasping its structure and system, without assimilating, at least on a subconscious level, its patterns and analogies. A child grasps these patterns, connects words into phrases, and even forms new words in strict accordance with the laws of word formation. By speaking, reading, and listening, a child gradually not only accumulates linguistic material but also internalizes its laws. As a result, a person develops what is known as a linguistic sense, without which it is impossible to achieve either high literacy or a cultured speech.

The principle of assessing the expressiveness of speech presupposes, along with an understanding of the informational function of linguistic means, an understanding of the expressive (stylistic) function, an understanding not only of the semantic but also of the emotional nuances and colorings of words and turns of speech, metaphors and other tropes, and other means of artistic expression.

Adherence to this principle presupposes the use of fiction in language teaching, as well as other texts that clearly express functional and stylistic features. This material promotes awareness of the emotional and semantic subtleties of the text.

The principle of accumulating oral language ahead of written language also reflects the natural pattern of human speech development and serves as a defining factor in the development of language teaching methods[16].

Properly organizing literacy instruction requires a specialized assessment of children's language and speech readiness for learning. What is a modern seven-year-old entering first grade like in terms of language development? How can children's readiness for literacy be assessed?

The teacher gets to know their future students through lively conversation, asks the children questions, invites them to talk about something, read something, or write something, and explores the children's general knowledge.

To account for the results of this introduction, the following chart can be created for assessing speech readiness for school:

1. Reading Ability:

- Reads whole words.
- Reads by syllables (analytical reading).
- Reads by letters (incorrect reading skill).
- Knows at least half the letters, but does not read.
- Knows less than half the letters, does not read.
- Knows only individual letters.

2. Writing Ability:

- Can write all letters, writes words (printed or written).
- Can write only some letters (printed or written).
- Cannot write at all.

3. Readiness for sound analysis:

- Correctly identifies the stressed syllable (or sound).
- Divides words into syllables.
- Distinguishes sounds within a word or syllable.
- Pronounces all sounds correctly.
- Pronounces sounds incorrectly (specify which ones).
- Speech volume, diction.

4. Oral Coherent Speech. Poetry Recitation:

- Knows at least three poems and readily recites them.
- Knows one or two poems. Is shy about reciting.
- Does not know any poems by heart.

5. Oral Coherent Speech. Storytelling:

- Can tell one or more stories.

- Attempts to tell stories, but fails.
- Cannot and does not attempt to tell a story.

6. Oral Coherent Speech. Length of Statements ("Tell me what you see in the picture"):

- Coherent story, more than 20 words, several sentences.
- From 10 to 20 words, several sentences.
- Coherent response of up to ten words.
- Monosyllabic response of two or three words.

The children's activity is also studied (whether they start talking, ask questions, answer questions, at length or in monosyllables, etc.), the syntactic structure of their speech, and the range of words they use.

All collected data is recorded in two ways: for each student individually, which is necessary for an individualized or differentiated approach to teaching, and for the entire class as a whole, to obtain "average" characteristics. The latter are necessary for selecting a methodology for whole-class work in the lesson.

Sound is the foundation of literacy instruction. Lessons include sound analysis of words and syllables, sound synthesis of words and syllables, sound analysis and articulation, diction work, and speech therapy[8].

Sound work is closely linked with letter work, especially in synthesis techniques (forming words from letters of the split alphabet and other techniques): the constant correlation of sound and letter is useful both for developing reading skills and for developing the foundations of correct spelling.

In first grade, even during the literacy period, work begins on developing the ability to identify the stressed syllable in a word. To correctly perceive the lexical meaning of a word, one of the syllables must be pronounced with greater force when reading it. In their speech practice, preschoolers pronounce most words correctly (meaning the stressed pronunciation of one of the syllables). However, isolating this syllable from the word or identifying the stressed syllable in the word is beyond the capabilities of first-graders until specialized training. The ability to identify the stressed syllable in a

word is associated with the development of analytical thinking, develops slowly, and requires systematic practice. Example exercise:

- The teacher pronounces a word and asks students to identify the number of syllables in the word, whichever is stressed.
- Identify the stressed syllable in the words and pronounce them correctly: briefcase, carrot, store, sorrel, bullfinch, thicket.
- Copy only words with the stress on the first syllable (selective copying).
- Select words with the stress on the second syllable, etc.

To develop grammatical concepts, students must develop the ability to abstract, to move away from the specific lexical meaning of words and to group them together, taking into account the common grammatical features inherent in all words in this group (for example, all words that answer the questions "who?" "what?" are grouped into the category "nouns." What all these words have in common is that they denote objects, do not change by gender, most of them change by number and case, etc.) [9].

Mastering grammatical concepts is a lengthy and rather complex process for young schoolchildren. When organizing work on concepts in elementary grades, teachers consider the linguistic essence of the concept being studied, the psychological and didactic characteristics of the learning process in young schoolchildren, the interdependence of students' verbal and intellectual development, and the role of grammatical knowledge in speech practice.

Grammatical concepts summarize the essential features of linguistic phenomena. Therefore, the process of mastering a concept should primarily include an analysis of specific linguistic material in order to identify the essential characteristics of the concept being studied. Essential characteristics are distinctive features necessary for a given concept, without which the concept as such cannot exist (they constitute its essence, its very essence).

For example, an ending as a morpheme is characterized by two essential features:

- a) an ending is a variable part of a word,

- b) it performs a syntactic function (serves to connect words in a sentence) or a form-forming function (book is singular, books are plural).

However, this does not mean that the characteristics of this concept are limited to the above features. An ending has a number of nonessential features, i.e., features that may be present in some words but absent in others. Thus, an ending most often appears at the end of a word, but there are also words in which an ending is followed by a suffix (stroitsya, sobrat'sya). In some words, an ending, along with its grammatical role, also performs a word-forming function (physics is a science, a physicist is a person engaged in this science; similarly, biology is a biologist, mathematics is a mathematician). In a word, the ending can be indicated by a letter or letters, i.e., expressed materially, but it can also be zero (water - shore). When beginning work on a concept, the teacher clearly defines its essential features, taking into account the curriculum requirements, clarifying which features (essential or non-essential) should be introduced to students in a given class, and which vocabulary, teaching methods, and tools are best to use[7].

After the essential features of the concept being studied have been identified through analysis of the linguistic material (the first stage of concept development), it is necessary to establish connections between them and correlate them with one another. These relationships are considered properties of the same concept and introduce a term (the second stage of concept development).

Discovering the features of a concept and introducing a term does not mean that students have grasped the essence of the concept. Students must be able to accurately formulate definitions of the concept and transfer its features to new linguistic material—that is, be able to recognize the concept being studied and apply this knowledge in speech practice. Therefore, the third stage focuses on the precise formulation of the concept definition, while the fourth stage involves exercises in recognizing the category being studied among others. Students develop the ability to use the concept to solve practical problems (to accurately express thoughts, to correctly spell words and sentences, etc.) [11].

A mandatory component of the concept formation process includes gradually clarifying the lexical meaning of words for schoolchildren, their lexical compatibility with other words in sentences, and developing the ability to use words stylistically precisely in oral and written speech. Implementing this approach requires a basic introduction to the polysemy of words, their literal and figurative use, and synonyms and antonyms.

Thus, when developing grammatical concepts, on the one hand, it is necessary to develop students' ability to abstract from the lexical meaning of specific words and synthesize the general, grammatical meaning characteristic of words as a specific linguistic category. On the other hand, it is important to develop a deep understanding of the lexical meaning of words in schoolchildren. Otherwise, the application of acquired grammatical knowledge will be too narrow and distant from real-life speech practice and direct use for communication.

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